

THE POTENTIAL BIO BASED POLYMER AND THEIR NANOCOMPOSITES FOR COMPOSITES STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY

In this work, new formulations of cellulose fiber composites based on polypropylene (PP) have been developed for melt processing. This new approach allows eliminating the cellulose drying step and the safety challenge related to the high flammability of the dried cellulose source thus reducing sufficiently the overall processing energy and cost. In addition it can also improve significantly the mechanical properties and the flame resistance of the composites.

Keywords: cellulose fiber, composites, formulation, processing, characterization.

INTRODUCTION

Cellulose fiber composites have been used extensively for the construction industries in North America and they began to receive very much attraction in Europe, South America and Asia. In order to increase the competitiveness, it is important for the composites industry to reduce the consumption of energy and cost as well as to improve output and performance.

This paper presents a new method to overcome cellulose humidity and improve the mechanical properties and fire resistance of cellulose composites in which basic oxide filler is used. In principle, the humidity and wood acidity are absorbed or neutralized by adding basic oxides, such as calcium oxide, during processing. As a result, no drying of wood is required and degradation is limited.

EXPERIMENTAL

Different grades of PP, both virgin and recycle, and coupling agents (CA) based on maleic anhydride (MA) grafted polypropylene, such as Epolene-43, Epolene-3015 (E3015), and Epolene-3003 (E3003) all from Eastman Chemicals, were used in this study. Different spruce sawdusts were provided by JER Envirotech (Canada) while rice husk and flax fibers were kindly provided by Northern Wild Rice and Schweitzer-Mauduit Canada, respectively. Calcium oxide (CaO) and aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) were supplied by C. P. Hall Company and Malakof Industries Inc., respectively.

The composites were prepared by a twin-screw extrusion Spec W&P 30 mm having L/D = 40, speed = 150-175 rpm, T max = 185°C. Samples were molded by injection at T = 200°C. All samples contained 40 wt% cellulose fibers and 2 wt% coupling agent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interface in the composite without coupling agent appears very poor but with the presence of coupling agent, the interface is significantly improved and it becomes the best when the additive filler is added (in addition with the coupling agent) (Fig.1). The additive filler can minimize the degradation of the fibers and it also contributes to the mechanical performance as reinforcing filler.

As a result of improving compatibility between the matrix and the flax fibers, coupling agents have improved significantly the strength and modulus of the composites prepared by compression. The MA grafting amount and molecular weight of coupling agent has definitely an effect on the performance and a superior performance with the presence of reactive filler was also found in Figure 2. The reinforcing effect of flax fibers and reactive fillers are also confirmed in the extruded samples.

CONCLUSIONS

The results show that the presence of basic oxides combined with coupling agent significantly improves the mechanical performance and fire resistance of the cellulose composites. These oxides absorb the humidity and neutralize the acidity of the wood reinforcement, thus limiting the degradation during compounding. The short-chain coupling agent E43 provides a better advantage since it has a higher mobility to impregnate the wood particle surface. While its high maleic anhydride content allows a better interaction with the basic fillers, thus enhance the reinforcing effect of the fillers. It was also found that CaO is one of the best fillers for cellulose composites due to its high reactivity and low cost. With this new development, the cost of the materials, the cost of processing and the emission of green house gas should reduce dramatically.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial provided from Agriculture Agri-Food Canada via the ABIP Network and from the National Research Council Canada via the National Bioproducts Program.